
Leadership Diversity and Team Effectiveness in Niger Delta University

Onyinyechi Victoria Ndubueze

*College of Business, Technology and Engineering
Sheffield Hallam University, UK*

Abstract

The university system in Nigeria is saddled with enormous leadership challenges, such as bad leadership styles of Vice Chancellors resulting to ineffectiveness of academic and non-academic staff. The purpose of this study is to examine the influence of leadership diversity on team effectiveness in Niger Delta University. The study used two thousand, one hundred and two (2,102) employees as study population, and a sample of three hundred and thirty-six employees. Three hundred and thirty-six (336) copies of questionnaire were administered to academic and non-academic staff of the university and Three hundred (300) copies were retrieved. Statistical analysis was conducted using Spearman Rank Order Correlation Coefficient to test the hypotheses. The findings of the study revealed that transformational and transactional leadership styles positively impact both measures of team effectiveness (goal achievement and problem-solving) in the University, while democratic leadership as a dimension of leadership diversity positively impact on goal achievement and negative impact on problem solving within the University. The study recommends that university leaders should regularly assess their leadership skills. And the results of these surveys and leaders' self-evaluations should be considered when planning leadership development or training initiatives inside the institution.

Keywords: Leadership Diversity, Team Effectiveness, Transformational, Transactional, Democratic, Goal Achievement, Problem-Solving

1.0 Introduction

Universities are acknowledged to play a critical role in all economies throughout the globe nowadays. Universities have long been recognized as development engines, developing individual ability, job creation, and economic progress across the globe. According to Ali (2010), universities contribute to the growth and improvement of society and aid the community that hosts them in having a democratic voice in the globalization process. According to Brennan et al. (2004), the location of a university in an area will offer job possibilities for both skilled and unskilled labour, which will increase the population of the town as a consequence of individuals moving into the town to seek work. Universities also contribute to growth in economic activity, changes in construction conditions, and assist in dealing with educational trends (Brennan et al., 2004). According to Hayward (2006), active engagement in knowledge societies is critical to economic progress, and higher education institutions, such as universities, are potential engines for such growth. As a result, the degree to which the profits are reaped is determined by the attention provided to universities by the south-south areas. However, despite the numerous benefits universities bring to the region where they are located, there have been persistent and recurring issues of team ineffectiveness among university staffs, which has severely hampered the achievements of these universities. According to Ogunode (2018), universities in Nigeria are confronted with various issues such as lack of solid strategic plan, bad leadership, poor research activities, inadequate infrastructural facilities, insufficient finance, and subpar laboratories. All of these difficulties have harmed the efficiency of teams at Niger Delta University. Mathieu et al. (2006) conducted research on team effectiveness to provide solutions to the recurring issue of team ineffectiveness. They proposed staff empowerment as a strategy to attaining team effectiveness. Baiden and DF (2010); Baiden and Price (2011) conducted a study on the influence of integration on team performance, indicating that integration is beneficial for boosting collaboration effectiveness. In addition, Gilson et al. (2005) conducted a study on creativity and standardization as potential drivers of team performance, indicating that innovation and standardized work practices promote team effectiveness. Despite these studies, the problem of team ineffectiveness among university employees in Nigeria's south-south institutions remains. Danish et al. (2015), stress the importance of leaders in developing team performance. As a result, it has become critical to investigate the link between leadership diversity and team performance.

Teams or workgroups have been identified as an organization's structural response to provide the flexible and efficient working that an organization requires to meet the demands of modern business in terms of heightened competition, the constant demand for innovations, growing job specializations, and the internalization of organization operations (Akmal, 2015; Brown, 2014; Solat et al., 2017). The degree to which a team accomplishes its goals, meets the needs and objectives of its members, and survives in an organization is referred to as team effectiveness (McShane.; et al., 2015). This puts team efficacy at the heart of organizational performance and effectiveness, with team's "cornerstone" or "mainstay" of organizational existence. Teams are utilized in businesses across all sectors and industries since it is recognized that they outperform people operating alone, particularly when performance demands many talents and judgments (Hayes, 2002; Scarnati, 2001). They have become the fundamental building elements for many corporate organizations, including colleges (Stewart & Barrick, 2000). The notion of teamwork, on the other hand, is dependent on the presence of synergies among the different team members in order to collectively and individually contribute to the formation of a successful team environment (Al-Rawi, 2008). Team members must be adaptable in both roles and duties in order to operate in a cooperative environment where objectives are attained collectively rather than competitively (Tarricone

& Luca, 2002).

Hoch (2013) proposed that a leader's conduct influences the structure, working process, and effectiveness of their teams. Danish et al. (2015) underline the critical role of leaders in creating team effectiveness, which is at the heart of successfully carrying out needed activities for an organization's overall performance. Universities are not an exception in Nigeria's south-south area. Leadership diversity has been studied based on demographic criteria such as the leader's age, gender, ethnicity, and educational background, as well as psychological characteristics such as the leader's values and leadership style (Lawrence, 1997). However, for the sake of this paper, leadership diversity will be examined based on leadership style. According to Aldoshan (2016), "leadership style and teamwork are extremely strongly associated," with teamwork being a consequence in contexts managed with the right leadership style. In that way, how workers modify their behaviour in reaction to the work atmosphere set by the leader may have an impact on team performance (Akmal, 2015; Makaske, 2015). As a result, encouraging collaboration among university personnel is impossible when the leader demonstrates the improper leadership style in a specific setting. Given that teams do not form or exist organically, optimal team composition in terms of putting together team members with essential and complimentary talents in the context of the objective to be attained would necessitate the right leadership style (Ekung et al., 2015). Appropriate leadership is therefore essential in south-south institutions to recruit and retain talented individuals, as well as to successfully integrate these abilities to form productive teams. The goal of this research is to investigate the relationship between leadership diversity and team effectiveness in Niger Delta University.

Statement of the problem

Niger Delta University has faced several issues that have hampered its development, individual capacity building, goal attainment, and economic contribution to the nation. According to Udida et al. (2009), university systems are confronted with several challenges, including inadequate finance, insufficient curriculum coordination, leadership issues, and lack of infrastructural amenities. Niger Delta University has suffered enormous leadership challenges, such as bad leadership styles of Vice Chancellors. Many leaders of the university rose without appropriate procedure; they are chosen by politicians with limited leadership skills to manage academic institutions such as universities. They lack the competence, leadership, and administrative abilities needed to restructure universities for sustainability, which has resulted in a slew of additional issues. Another issue confronting Niger Delta University is that it lacks international recognition. According to Adeniyi et al. (2012), the National Universities Commission, which is tasked with overseeing institutions in Nigeria, is not performing well in rebranding and repackaging Nigerian universities overseas.

According to Ojo (2018), poor infrastructure facilities are another important constraint to the educational growth of institutions in Nigeria. According to John (2016), infrastructural facilities and laboratory equipment at our institutions are in poor shape, with the majority of them being obsolete. All the resources necessary for the educational production process are in low supply, which impedes learning and research. The lack of infrastructure at the university is appalling, and it falls short of providing a perfect academic environment. Students nowadays are studying in decaying facilities. Another issue affecting Niger Delta University is a bleak worldwide view. Furthermore, the number of foreign students and faculty at the university is low, and many academics in Niger Delta University are not involved in international collaboration with other universities for the aim of exchanging ideas and transferring knowledge. The incapacity of the university to recruit students, postgraduates,

and teachers from all over the world demonstrates that the Niger Delta University lack the qualities that would draw diverse nationals into their institutions. Hill and Grossman (2013) stated that owing to security concerns and a bad working environment, many foreign teachers teaching in Nigerian colleges have returned to their home countries. Another important issue plaguing Nigerian universities is a lack of a solid strategic strategy. Ojo (2018) concurs when he observes that university academic programs are not well structured. Ogunode (2018) also stated that academic programs in universities are poorly implemented owing to a lack of appropriate strategies.

According to Ogunode (2020), the quality of teaching and learning at Nigerian colleges is low, and instructional effectiveness cannot be guaranteed. Eneh and Owo (2017) noted that although student enrollment rises in tandem with the national population, additional personnel are not hired at the same pace. As a result, the student-teacher ratio becomes unmanageable. All these problems have had a detrimental impact on the effectiveness of teams in Nigeria tertiary institutions. This study therefore seeks to investigate leadership diversity and team effectiveness in Niger Delta University.

Research Questions

The study seeks to provide answers to the following research questions:

- i. Is there a relationship between transformation leadership and goal achievement?
- ii. Is there a relationship between transformation leadership and problem solving?
- iii. Is there a relationship between transactional leadership and goal achievement?
- iv. Is there a relationship between transactional leadership and problem solving?
- v. Is there a relationship between democratic leadership and goal achievement?
- vi. Is there a relationship between democratic leadership and problem solving?

Research Hypotheses

The following null research hypotheses were formulated and tested:

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between transformation leadership and goal achievement.

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between transformation leadership and problem solving.

H₀₃: There is no significant relationship between transactional leadership and goal achievement.

H₀₄: There is no significant relationship between transactional leadership and problem solving.

H₀₅: There is no significant relationship between democratic leadership and goal achievement

H₀₆: There is no significant relationship between democratic leadership and problem solving

2.0 Literature Review

Leadership Diversity

Leader and leadership are two of the most commonly debated and investigated ideas in workplaces (Kuchler, 2008). This might be because the existence and prospering of any group or team is entirely reliant on leadership. Leader and leadership have numerous meanings in the existing corpus of literature. Starting with leadership, it has generally been defined as an individual's qualities or abilities that are valuable in operating an organization (Nivala & Hujala, 2002). According to this definition, leadership entails an individual(s) influencing an organization's activities, which may or may not include the direction of labour or the use of money and other resources controlled by the organization. According to Cole (2002), leadership is a continually changing process in terms of time, structure, and forms of

organization that requires a person to influence a group of individuals in order to reach an ultimate goal. Gill (2006) provided a more organization-oriented definition of leadership as including a person who supports by exciting, motivating, and encouraging followers in order to accomplish outcomes that meet the existence and aim of an organization. As a result, Lok and Crawford (2004) feel that CEOs have a significant influence in determining whether a firm succeeds or fails. Leadership diversity has been studied based on demographic criteria such as the leader's age, gender, race, and educational background (Lawrence, 1997), as well as psychological characteristics such as the leader's values and leadership style (Sharfman et al., 2000). Leadership style refers to the many approaches to leadership in workplaces. Administrative style, authoritarian style, charismatic style, free economy style, democratic style, situational style, cooperative style, relationship-based style, transactional style, transformational style, etc (Mosadeghrad, 2003). Literature abounds with evidence that leaders adopt different leadership styles in various contexts, based on company culture and employee maturity. Today's university workers, on the other hand, are primarily specialized and well educated, which dictates the sort of influence they seek from their leader. This study examined three leadership styles: transformational, transactional, and democratic leadership styles.

Transformational Leadership

Transformational leadership is a leadership style in which the leader encourages followers to outperform their initial performance expectations by promoting changes in their values, norms, and personal interests (e.g., from simply pursuing stable employment or job promotions, to going further by sharing their expertise and knowledge on a voluntary basis to improve organizational effectiveness (Aryee et al. (2012). Transformational leadership is made up of four distinct but interconnected behavioural components: idealized influence, which refers to leaders' distinct behaviours that instill pride and respect in employees through association with the leader, inspirational motivation, which refers to leaders' behaviours that encourage employee motivation by enriching individual and organizational-level vision and spirit, intellectual stimulation, which refers to leaders' behaviours that encourage non-tradable thinking (Braun et al., 2013).

Transformational leaders communicate personal morals and corporate ethics with their colleagues, resulting in increased intrinsic drive and organizational commitment. Intrinsic motivation promotes creative problem solving and improved team performance by emphasizing the long-term vision that connects team members (Chen et al., 2013). Team members that are intrinsically motivated see themselves as a single body, sharing their knowledge of work duties and how to best fulfill them, expressing numerous unique ideas at every stage of team-level work and, as a result, enhancing team performance (Aryee et al., 2012). Employees that regard their boss as a role model will strive to innovate and be proactive in sharing their ideas with the team, resulting in increased team performance (Pearce & Sims Jr, 2002).

Transactional Leadership

Transactional leadership is a form of leadership that focuses on interactions between leaders and team members. According to Bass et al. (2003), transactional leadership qualities include dependent compensation and exception management. Transactional leaders monitor deviations from established norms and take remedial action to meet company objectives via exception management. When a leader swaps anything of economic, political, or psychological value with team members, this is referred to as transactional leadership. These exchanges are predicated on the leader setting performance standards and outlining the

circumstances under which incentives are available for fulfilling these requirements, and transactional behaviours may help the leader achieve his or her goals while also satisfying the interests of the team (House et al., 2004). Transactional leadership involves team members in an agreement that defines the performance expectations of the followers as well as the penalties for fulfilling those standards. Followers who are secure in their job expectations are more inclined to go above and beyond the official performance.

According to Yukl (2006), transactional leadership is a leadership style that focuses on transactions between leaders and team members. Transactional leadership encourages and motivates team members by trading a reward for certain performance. With a transactional leader, members of the team are offered benefits if they execute their obligations in line with team agreements. In other words, the transactional leader motivates team members to work, which increases team performance.

Democratic Leadership

This is a participative leadership style that reflects principles and processes such as self-determination and equal participation. However, democratic leaders should not be compared to elected officials. These leaders facilitate group decision making by involving their team members and providing them with support and options. Furthermore, unlike the authoritarian style, this leadership style is defined by teamwork, active engagement, accountability, and delegation of duties and tasks. The empowering of team members, the division of responsibilities, and the facilitation of group debates are all important functions of democratic leadership. Team members are held responsible for their judgments, actions, and desire to preserve the independence and autonomy of the group (Avolio et al., 2009). This leadership approach, however, might fail when duties are not clearly defined and time is restricted. Democratic leadership is effective when team members are willing to share their experience and knowledge.

According to Robbins (2000), democratic leadership styles support collaborative decision-making. This demonstrates the likelihood that such a leader may get the cooperation of the team and positively inspire them. The democratic leader's choices are not as unilateral as those of the autocrat since they are the result of dialogue with and involvement of group members. It may be argued that this technique works best when the leader knows a portion of the knowledge and the workers have the remainder. As a result, a leader cannot be expected to know everything; this is why firms hire informed and skilled personnel. Using this technique benefits both parties since it helps workers to become part of the team and allows the leader to make better judgment.

Team Effectiveness

A team is an active entity that is united by a shared purpose or objective that must be attained. According to Mician and Rodger (2000), teams are made up of individuals whose skill sets complement each other and work together to achieve common objectives for which the group feels responsibility. Team effectiveness is a wide phrase that may be simply described as the ability of a group of individuals working together to achieve predetermined goals or aims. However, existing research agrees that a full grasp of the word would include defining 'efficacy' on several levels (Cooke & Hilton, 2015; Mician & Rodger, 2000). To correctly assess team effectiveness, Mician and Rodger (2000) advocate determining what effectiveness means at the organizational, process, and person levels of a team. Similarly, Cooke and Hilton (2015) highlight that team performance must be defined at the individual, group, and higher-level impacts. According to Mician and Rodger (2000), team success in

the organizational dimension comprises clarity of purpose and enough resources under an acceptable culture and competent leadership, with specific duties and clear roles for relevant members. From a process standpoint, team effectiveness is primarily concerned with limiting team conflict via appropriate coordination and clear communication in a unified atmosphere that allows for strong social interactions, shared decision making, and healthy performance feedback. At the individual level, team performance requires individuals who offer a depth of technical competence and self-knowledge, are willing to trust other team members, are devoted to team values and goals, and are flexible enough to cope with changes in team dynamics as they arise.

Sundstrom (2000) discussed team effectiveness in terms of teams satisfying the performance standards or expectations of multiple stakeholders who are influenced by the team's output. Several stakeholders will have different expectations or requirements. The efficacy of a team will be rated by the customer based on the quality of service in terms of cost, timeliness of service, and personalization of customer experience as delivered by various team members throughout multiple transactions with the company. For the manager, team effectiveness will mean team members taking the initiative to solve issues as they emerge with as little oversight as possible. This study considered goal achievement and problem-solving as two measures of team effectiveness.

Goal Achievement

Goal achievement summarizes team members' behaviours in relation to their key goals. The degree to which a team accomplishes its aims or objectives, as well as the requirements and objectives of its members, is referred to as goal achievement. A team is a collection of individuals who are structured to work together to accomplish group and organizational goals. A team is a small group of individuals with complementary abilities who are dedicated to a single objective, common performance goals, and a method for which they are mutually responsible (Acharya & Steffen, 2015). In today's post-industrial age, an increasing number of firms are operating in high-velocity settings that are marked by rapid change, uncertainty, and high risk (Riolfi-Saltzman & Luthans, 2001). Many firms use the team idea to fulfill organizational goals in such a highly dynamic and unpredictable environment, and teams are efficient and productive (LePine et al., 2002). A team managed by an ineffective leader with a bad leadership style will not accomplish its objectives or goals of the business. Resources and team (collective) responsibility are employed for the outcome or objective reached via the combined and collective work of members, and teams are also established for challenges as well as to compete with competitors. Teams are created to profit from the synergy principle, which states that total team production is always more than the sum of individual output or goal attainment of team members, i.e. one plus one in a productive and dynamic team is always greater than two (O'Leary-Kelly et al., 2002). Goal achievement is future-directed cognitive representations of desired outcomes in achievement situations that differ in how achievement is conceptualized (Chazan et al., 2022)

Problem-Solving

Problem solving is the process of overcoming difficulties that appears to interfere with the attainment of goal. It is a procedure of making adjustment instead of interference (Skinner, 1953). Problem-solving is the cognitive process of finding a means to achieve goals (Mefoh et al., 2017) Problem-solving is a high-level thinking skill that requires the ability to identify the nature of a problem, deconstruct it, and develop an effective set of actions to address the challenges related to it (Abazov, 2016; Oliveri, 2017), which should be provided to students in the increasingly complex world (Sutarno et al., 2017). Docktor et al. (2016) developed the

problem-solving steps into five steps, as follows: focusing on the problems, describing them as concepts, planning the solutions, implementing the plans, and evaluating the solutions. The process involves understanding the problem (Meyer, 2014), choosing the proper concept, and checking the problem's suitability with the proposed solution (Gunawan et al., 2020). It requires a good understanding of concepts and high-level thinking skills (Hermansyah et al., 2019).

Punhagui (2019) also developed problem-solving steps and stated that the problem-solving cycles are as follows: identifying a problem by recognizing the goal to be reached; defining and representing it to understand how to solve it; elaborating a strategy for solving the problem by planning ways to solve it; organizing information on a problem by integrating the necessary information for meeting the challenge; allocating resources by using time, space, materials, and knowledge; monitoring by measuring and evaluating the taken steps during the course; and evaluating the solution after being concluded (Punhagui, 2019). An effective team is made up of people who work together to solve a problem while minimizing disagreement. Team choices and how team members contribute to higher quality judgments and more innovative solutions to both group and organizational challenges make teams more productive than individuals (Acharya & Steffen, 2015). A team's success or failure is totally dependent on the team leader. To be successful in addressing organizational challenges, a team must have effective leadership, adequate work distribution, and members who understand their roles (McShane.; et al., 2015). A successful team-based company is dynamic and always ready to modify and re-orient its core strengths to meet new challenges.

Theoretical Framework

Theory of Transformational Leadership (TTL)

The theory of transformational leadership was first introduced by James MacGregor Burns in 1978 in his descriptive research on political leaders. According to Burns, transforming leadership is a process in which "leaders and followers help each other to advance to a higher level of morale and motivation". Burns related to the difficulty in differentiation between management and leadership and claimed that the differences are in characteristics and behaviours. He established two concepts: "transforming leadership" and "transactional leadership" (Ghasabeh et al., 2015). According to Burns, the transforming approach creates significant change in the life of people and organizations. It redesigns perceptions and values, and changes expectations and aspirations of employees. Transforming leaders are idealized in the sense that they are a moral exemplar of working towards the benefit of the team, organization and/or community. Transformational leaders can try to change organizational culture. Transformational leadership is defined as a leadership approach that causes change in individuals and social systems (Ghasabeh et al., 2015). It creates valuable and positive change in the followers with the end goal of developing followers into leaders. Transformational leadership enhances the motivation, morale and performance of followers through a variety of mechanisms. These include connecting the follower's sense of identity and self to the mission and the collective identity of the organization; being a role model for followers that inspires them; challenging followers to take greater ownership for their work, and understanding the strengths and weaknesses of followers, so the leader can align followers with tasks that optimize their performance (Berkovich, 2016).

Bernard M. Bass in 1985 extended the work of Burns by explaining the psychological mechanisms that underlie transforming leadership; Bass used the term "transformational" instead of "transforming." Bass in his work explained how transformational leadership could be measured, as well as how it impacts follower motivation and performance. He opined that

the extent to which a leader is transformational is measured first, in terms of his influence on the followers. The followers of such a leader feel trust, admiration, loyalty and respect for the leader and because of the qualities of the transformational leader are willing to work harder than originally expected. These outcomes occur because the transformational leader offers followers something more than just working for self-gain; they provide followers with an inspiring mission and vision and give them an identity (Korejan & Shahbazi, 2016). The leader transforms and motivates followers through his or her idealized influence (earlier referred to as charisma), intellectual stimulation and individual consideration. In addition, this leader encourages followers to come up with new and unique ways to challenge the status quo and to alter the environment to support being successful. In contrast to Burns, Bass suggested that leadership can simultaneously display both transformational and transactional leadership. Research has shown that transformational leadership positively predicts a wide variety of performance outcomes including individual, group and organizational level variables (Rolfe, 2011).

3.0 Methodology

This study population is two thousand one hundred and two (2102) and a sample size of 336 was derived using the Taro Yamane formula. Data was collected from academic and non-academic staff of the university using structured questionnaire. A bi-variate data analysis was done with a non-parametric test- Spearman Rank Order Correlation Coefficient.

Statistical Testing of Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1 (H₀₁): There is no significant relationship between transformational leadership and goal achievement.

Table 1: Results of Spearman Rank Order Correlation Coefficient for items of transformational leadership influence and goal achievement.

			Correlations	
			TRNSF_LD	GOAL_ACH
Spearman's rho	TRNSF_LD	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	-.051
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.379
		N	300	300
	GOAL_ACH	Correlation Coefficient	-.051	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.379	.
		N	300	300

In connection with hypothesis 1, correlation analysis was conducted with transformational leadership as the independent variable and goal achievement as the dependent variable. Results show that $t_{cal} = 0.379$ and t_{tab} at 5% = 0.05. Since $t_{cal} > t_{tab}$, we reject the null hypothesis that transformational leadership parameter is not statistically significant to goal achievement at 5% level of significance. From the table above, the p-value of 0.379 is greater than the critical value at 5% = 0.05 level of significance; hence the study rejects the null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between transformational leadership and goal achievement in Niger Delta University (NDU), Bayelsa State. The correlation coefficient of -5.1% shows a weak negative relationship between the variables.

Hypothesis 2 (H0₂): There is no significant relationship between transformational leadership and problem solving.

Table 2: Results of Spearman Rank Order Correlation Coefficient for items of transformational leadership and problem solving.

			TRNSF_LD	PROB_SOLV
Spearman's rho	TRNSF_LD	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	.059
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.304
		N	300	300
	PROB_SOLV	Correlation Coefficient	.059	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.304	.
		N	300	300

In connection with hypothesis 2, correlation analysis was conducted with transformational leadership as the independent variable and problem solving as the dependent variable. Results show that $t_{cal} = 0.304$ and t_{tab} at 5% = 0.05. Since $t_{cal} > t_{tab}$, we reject the null hypothesis, that transformational leadership parameter is not statistically significant to problem solving at 5% level of significance. From the table above, the p-value of 0.304 is greater than the critical value at 5% = 0.05 level of significance; hence the study rejects the null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between transformational leadership and problem solving in Niger Delta University (NDU), Bayelsa State. The correlation coefficient of 5.9% shows a weak positive relationship between the variables.

Hypothesis 3 (H0₃): There is no significant relationship between transactional leadership and goal achievement.

Table 3: Results of Spearman Rank Order Correlation Coefficient for between transactional leadership and goal achievement.

			TRNSAC_LD	GOAL_ACH
Spearman's rho	TRNSAC_LD	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	.014
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.809
		N	300	300
	GOAL_ACH	Correlation Coefficient	.014	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.809	.
		N	300	300

For hypothesis 3, correlation analysis was conducted with transactional leadership as the independent variable and goal achievement as the dependent variable. Results show that $t_{cal} = 0.809$ and t_{tab} at 5% = 0.05. Since $t_{cal} > t_{tab}$, we reject the null hypothesis, that transactional leadership parameter is not statistically significant to goal achievement at 5% level of significance. From the table above, the p-value of 0.809 is greater than the critical value at 5% = 0.05 level of significance; hence the study rejects the null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between transactional leadership and goal achievement in Niger Delta University (NDU), Bayelsa State. The correlation coefficient of 1.4% shows a weak positive

relationship between the variables.

Hypothesis 4 (H₀₄): There is no significant relationship between transactional leadership and problem solving.

Table 4: Results of Spearman Rank Order Correlation Coefficient for items transactional leadership and problem solving.

			TRNSAC_LD	PROB_SOLV
Spearman's rho	TRNSAC_LD	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	-.051
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.378
		N	300	300
	PROB_SOLV	Correlation Coefficient	-.051	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.378	.
		N	300	300

For hypothesis 4, correlation analysis was conducted with transactional leadership as the independent variable and problem solving as the dependent variable. Results show that $t_{cal} = 0.378$ and t_{tab} at 5%=0.05. Since $t_{cal} > t_{tab}$, we reject the null hypothesis that transactional leadership parameter is not statistically significant to problem solving at 5% level of significance. From the table above, the p-value of 0.378 is greater than the critical value at 5% = 0.05 level of significance; hence the study rejects the null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between transactional leadership and goal achievement in Niger Delta University (NDU), Bayelsa State. The correlation coefficient of -5.1% shows a weak negative relationship between the variables.

Hypothesis 5 (H₀₅): There is no significant relationship between democratic leadership and goal achievement.

Table 5: Results of Spearman Rank Order Correlation Coefficient for items of democratic leadership and goal achievement.

			DEMOC_LD	GOAL_ACH
Spearman's rho	DEMOC_LD	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	-.027
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.640
		N	300	300
	GOAL_ACH	Correlation Coefficient	-.027	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.640	.
		N	300	300

In hypothesis 5, correlation analysis was conducted with democratic leadership as the independent variable and goal achievement as the dependent variable. Results show that $t_{cal} = 0.640$ and t_{tab} at 5%=0.05. Since $t_{cal} > t_{tab}$, we reject the null hypothesis, that democratic leadership parameter is statistically significant to goal achievement at 5% level of significance. From the table above, the p-value of 0.640 is greater than the critical value at 5% = 0.05 level of significance; hence the study rejects the null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between democratic leadership and goal achievement in Niger Delta University (NDU), Bayelsa State. The correlation coefficient of -2.7% shows a weak negative

relationship between the variables.

Hypothesis 6 (H₀): There is no significant relationship between democratic leadership and problem solving.

Table 6. Results of Spearman Rank Order Correlation Coefficient for items of democratic leadership and problem solving.

			DEMOC_LD	PROB_SOLV
Spearman's rho	DEMOC_LD	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	.120
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.038
		N	300	300
	PROB_SOLV	Correlation Coefficient	.120	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.038	.
		N	300	300

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

In hypothesis 6, correlation analysis was conducted with democratic leadership as the independent variable and problem solving as the dependent variable. Results show that $t_{cal} = 0.038$ and t_{tab} at 5% = 0.05. Since $t_{cal} < t_{tab}$, we accept the null hypothesis that democratic parameter is statistically significant to problem solving at 5% level of significance. From the table above, the p-value of 0.038 is less than the critical value at 5% = 0.05 level of significance; hence the study accepts the null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between democratic leadership and problem solving in Niger Delta University (NDU), Bayelsa State. The correlation coefficient of 12% shows a weak positive relationship between the variables.

Discussion of Findings

Hypotheses one and two sought to examine the relationship between transformational leadership and the measures of team effectiveness (goal achievement and problem solving). The analysis of data collected revealed that there is a positive relationship between transformational leadership and the measures of team effectiveness (goal achievement and problem solving). The implication of this is that as transformational leaders communicate personal morals and corporate ethics with their colleagues, it will result in increased intrinsic drive and organizational commitment (Tu et al., 2017), Which will promote creative problem solving and improved team performance.

Hypotheses three and four sought to examine the relationship between transactional leadership and the measures of team effectiveness (goal achievement and problem solving). The analysis of data collected revealed that there is a positive relationship between transactional leadership and the measures of team effectiveness (goal achievement and problem solving). The implication of this is that as leaders encourage and motivate team members by trading reward for certain performance, in other words they offer benefits if employees execute their obligations in line with team agreements it will lead to increased team performance.

Hypotheses five and six sought to examine the relationship between democratic leadership and the measures of team effectiveness (goal achievement and problem solving). The analysis of data collected revealed that there is a positive relationship between

democratic leadership and goal achievement and a negative relationship between democratic leadership and problem solving. The implication of hypothesis five is that when leaders are self-determined, delegate duties and tasks, allow active engagement, accountability, equal participation; the organization will achieve its set objective or goal. While hypothesis six implies that democratic leadership style will not or have a limited chance of solving organizational problem.

4.0 Conclusion

The findings of this study revealed a positive relationship between leadership diversity and team effectiveness in Niger Delta University, Bayelsa state. Two dimensions of leadership diversity (transformational and transactional leadership) positively impact on team effectiveness in the University, while democratic leadership as a dimension of leadership diversity positively impact on goal achievement as one of the measures of team effectiveness and negative impact on problem solving within the University. This implies that breeding transformational leaders and transactional leaders who have the capacity to encourage, inspire, develop and motivate team members with exceptional leadership skills will produce improved results, solve problems and meet organizational set goal.

This finding supports the position of Gill (2006) that leadership refers to a person who supports by exciting, motivating, and encouraging followers in order to accomplish outcomes that meet the existence and aim of an organization. Cole (2002) noted that leadership is continually changing process in terms of time, structure, and forms of organization that require a person to influence a group of individuals to reach a goal.

The findings of the study also align with the assertion of Robbins (2000) that democratic leaders support collaborative decision-making. They are willing to share their experience and knowledge. They get the cooperation of their group and positively inspire them.

5.0 Recommendations

Based on the outcomes of this study, it was therefore recommended that:

- i. University leaders ought to be compelled to regularly assess their leadership skills. Employee impressions of leadership should be regularly surveyed by higher education institutions. The results of these surveys and leaders' self-evaluations should be considered when planning leadership development or training initiatives inside the organization.
- ii. Team leaders ought to be more involved in university human resources procedures, where they are asked for their opinions on the qualities the business should look for in candidates. This would significantly help to guarantee that the hiring practices of the universities align with the talent needs expressed by the team leaders who need to interact with employees to achieve the university's objective. In this regard, team leaders and the university's human resources department should discuss the talent needs of the groups before hiring people who meet the team's needs. The school management should employ people based on competence and not on political or personal grounds.
- iii. Management of NDU should look out for leaders who can communicate personal morals and corporate ethics with their colleagues, it will result in increased intrinsic drive and organizational commitment.
- iv. The school should support leaders who can persuade people and organizations to make changes and reform the institution to provide social amenities, a curriculum, and standards that are comparable to those of other countries.

References

- Abazov, R. (2016). How to improve your problem-solving skills. .
<https://www.researchgate.net/publication/305062877>
- Acharya, V. V., & Steffen, S. (2015). The “greatest” carry trade ever? Understanding eurozone bank risks. *Journal of Financial Economics*, 115(2), 215-236.
- Adeniyi, O. A., Omisakin, D., Olusegun, A., Egwaikhide, F., & Oyinlola, A. (2012). Foreign direct investment, economic growth and financial sector development in small open developing economies. *Economic Analysis & Policy*, 42(1).
- Akmal, K. (2015). Personality traits influence on team cohesiveness and performance: The moderating effect of leadership. *Information and knowledge management*,
- Al-Rawi, K. (2008). Cohesiveness within teamwork: the relationship to performance effectiveness—case study. *Education, Business and Society: Contemporary Middle Eastern Issues*, 1(2), 92-106.
- Aldoshan, K. (2016). Leadership styles promote teamwork. *International Journal of Scientific & Technology Research*, 5(06), 1-4.
- Ali, A. (2010). Developing the community: The role of universities and open and distance learning.
- Aryee, S., Walumbwa, F. O., Zhou, Q., & Hartnell, C. A. (2012). Transformational leadership, innovative behavior, and task performance: Test of mediation and moderation processes. *Human Performance*, 25(1), 1-25.
- Avolio, B. J., Walumbwa, F. O., & Weber, T. J. (2009). Leadership: Current theories, research, and future directions. *Annual review of psychology*, 60, 421-449.
- Baiden, & DF, A. (2010). The effect of integration on project delivery team effectiveness. *International Journal of Project Management*, 29(2), 129-136.
- Baiden, B. K., & Price, A. D. (2011). The effect of integration on project delivery team effectiveness. *International Journal of Project Management*, 29(2), 129-136.
- Bass, B. M., Avolio, B. J., Jung, D. I., & Berson, Y. (2003). Predicting unit performance by assessing transformational and transactional leadership. *Journal of applied psychology*, 88(2), 207.
- Berkovich, I. (2016). School leaders and transformational leadership theory: time to part ways? *Journal of Educational Administration*.
- Braun, S., Peus, C., Weisweiler, S., & Frey, D. (2013). Transformational leadership, job satisfaction, and team performance: A multilevel mediation model of trust. *The leadership quarterly*, 24(1), 270-283.
- Brennan, J., King, R., & Lebeau, Y. (2004). The role of universities in the transformation of societies. *Synthesis Report. Centre for Higher Education Research and Information/Association of Commonwealth Universities, UK*, 72.
- Brown, L. M. (2014). A proposed talent management model for Leader-Managers in State-Owned enterprises in China. *International Journal of Human Resource Studies*, 4(3), 198.
- Chazan, D. J., Pelletier, G. N., & Daniels, L. M. (2022). Achievement goal theory review: An application to school psychology. *Canadian Journal of School Psychology*, 37(1), 40-56.
- Chen, G., Farh, J.-L., Campbell-Bush, E. M., Wu, Z., & Wu, X. (2013). Teams as innovative systems: Multilevel motivational antecedents of innovation in R&D teams. *Journal of applied psychology*, 98(6), 1018.
- Cole, G. (2002). *Personnel and Human Resource Management 5th. London: Continuum.*
- Cooke, N. J., & Hilton, M. L. (2015). Enhancing the effectiveness of team science.

- Danish, R. Q., Aslam, N., Shahid, A. U., Bashir, F., & Tariq, S. (2015). Impact of team characteristics on team performance in banking sector of Pakistan. *The Journal of Commerce*, 7(4), 183.
- Docktor, J. L., Dornfeld, J., Frodermann, E., Heller, K., Hsu, L., Jackson, K. A., Mason, A., Ryan, Q. X., & Yang, J. (2016). Assessing student written problem solutions: A problem-solving rubric with application to introductory physics. *Physical review physics education research*, 12(1), 010130.
- Ekung, S., Olubajo, O. O., & Ebong, U. (2015). Influence of leadership Traits on Team performance as correlates of success in construction project delivery.
- Eneh, O. C., & Owo, N. J. (2017). Education Reforms in the Nigerian university System: A critique and suggested strategies. *Preface and acknowledgements*, 101.
- Ghasabeh, M. S., Soosay, C., & Reaiche, C. (2015). The emerging role of transformational leadership. *The Journal of Developing Areas*, 49(6), 459-467.
- Gill, R. (2006). *Theory and practice of leadership*. Sage Publications.
- Gilson, L. L., Mathieu, J. E., Shalley, C. E., & Ruddy, T. M. (2005). Creativity and standardization: complementary or conflicting drivers of team effectiveness? *Academy of Management journal*, 48(3), 521-531.
- Gunawan, G., Harjono, A., Nisyah, M. a., Kusdiastuti, M., & Herayanti, L. (2020). Improving Students' Problem-Solving Skills Using Inquiry Learning Model Combined with Advance Organizer. *International Journal of Instruction*, 13(4), 427-442.
- Hayes, N. (2002). *Managing Teams* (2nd ed.). Thomson Learning.
- Hayward, F. M. (2006). Quality assurance and accreditation of higher education in Africa. Conference on Higher Education Reform in Francophone Africa: Understanding the Keys of Success,
- Hermansyah, H., Gunawan, G., Harjono, A., & Adawiyah, R. (2019). Guided inquiry model with virtual labs to improve students' understanding on heat concept. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*,
- Hill, H., & Grossman, P. (2013). Learning from teacher observations: Challenges and opportunities posed by new teacher evaluation systems. *Harvard educational review*, 83(2), 371-384.
- Hoch, J. E. (2013). Shared leadership and innovation: The role of vertical leadership and employee integrity. *Journal of Business and Psychology*, 28(2), 159-174.
- House, R. J., Hanges, P. J., Javidan, M., Dorfman, P. W., & Gupta, V. (2004). *Culture, leadership, and organizations: The GLOBE study of 62 societies*. Sage publications.
- John, F. (2016). University development in Africa, the Nigerian experience. *Lagos: Light Press. Kemi, FT (2018) Supervision of Education in Nigeria. JSSE (3), 4.*
- Korejan, M. M., & Shahbazi, H. (2016). An analysis of the transformational leadership theory. *Journal of Fundamental and Applied Sciences*, 8(3), 452-461.
- Kuchler, W. J. (2008). Perceived leadership behavior and subordinates' job satisfaction in Midwestern NCAA Division III athletic departments. *The Sport Journal*, 11(2).
- Lawrence, B. S. (1997). Perspective—The black box of organizational demography. *Organization science*, 8(1), 1-22.
- LePine, J. A., Colquitt, J. A., & Erez, A. (2002). Adaptability to changing task contexts: Effects of general cognitive ability, conscientiousness, and openness to experience. *Personnel psychology*, 53(3), 563-593.
- Makaske, I. (2015). *The effect of leadership behavior on work climate and team effectiveness* [University of Twente].
- Mathieu, J. E., Gilson, L. L., & Ruddy, T. M. (2006). Empowerment and team effectiveness: An empirical test of an integrated model. *Journal of applied psychology*, 91(1), 97.

- McShane., L., S., Glinow., V., & A., M. (2015). *Organizational Behavior Emerging Knowledge, Global Reality*. McGraw-Hill.
- Mefoh, P. C., Nwoke, M. B., Chukwuorji, J. C., & Chijioke, A. O. (2017). Effect of cognitive style and gender on adolescents' problem solving ability. *Thinking Skills and Creativity*, 25, 47-52.
- Meyer, K. (2014). Making meaning in mathematics problem-solving using the Reciprocal Teaching approach. *Literacy learning: the middle years*, 22(2), 7-14.
- Mickan, S., & Rodger, S. (2000). Characteristics of effective teams: a literature review. *Australian Health Review*, 23(3), 201-208.
- Mosadeghrad, A. M. (2003). The role of participative management (suggestion system) in hospital effectiveness and efficiency. *Research in Medical Sciences*, 8(3), 85-89.
- Nivala, V., & Hujala, E. (2002). *Leadership in early childhood education: Cross-cultural perspectives*. Oulun yliopisto.
- O'Leary-Kelly, A. M., Martocchio, J. J., & Frink, D. D. (2002). A review of the influence of group goals on group performance. *Academy of Management journal*, 37(5), 1285-1301.
- Ogunode, N. J. (2018). An Investigation of the Challenges Facing the Planning of Basic Education in FCT, Abuja, Nigeria. *Electronic Research Journal of Behavioural Sciences*, 1.
- Ogunode, N. J. (2020). Nigerian universities and their sustainability: challenges and way forward. Available at SSRN 3695789.
- Ojo, A. A. (2018). *Higher Education in Nigeria*. House of Commons Palace of Westminster, London.
- Oliveri, M. E., Lawless, R., and Molloy, H. . (2017). A literature review on collaborative problem solving for college and workforce readiness. . Oliveri, M. E., Lawless, R., and Molloy, H. (2017). A literature review on collaborative problem solving for college and workforce readiness. *ETS Res. Rep. Ser. 2017*, 1–27. doi:10.1002/ets2.12133, 1-27.
- Pearce, C. L., & Sims Jr, H. P. (2002). Vertical versus shared leadership as predictors of the effectiveness of change management teams: An examination of aversive, directive, transactional, transformational, and empowering leader behaviors. *Group dynamics: Theory, research, and practice*, 6(2), 172.
- Punhagui, G. C. (2019). Using problem-solving as a method for the development of self-regulation of learning with adolescents: An experience report. In *Metacognition in Learning*. IntechOpen.
- Riolli-Saltzman, L., & Luthans, F. (2001). After the bubble burst: How small high-tech firms can keep in front of the wave. *Academy of Management Perspectives*, 15(3), 114-124.
- Robbins, S. P. (2000). *Organisational Behaviour* (6th ed.). Prentice Hall Englewood Cliffs.
- Rolfe, P. (2011). Transformational leadership theory: What every leader needs to know. *Nurse leader*, 9(2), 54-57.
- Scarnati, J. T. (2001). On becoming a team player. *Team performance management: An International journal*.
- Sharfman, M. P., Pinkston, T. S., & Sigerstad, T. D. (2000). The effects of managerial values on social issues evaluation: An empirical examination. *Business & Society*, 39(2), 144-182.
- Solat, S., Bashir, M., Ali, A., Baig, S. A., Hussain, Z., & Jamil, K. (2017). The impact of leadership style on group effectiveness: The mediating role of counterproductive behavior. *City University Research Journal*, 1-13.

- Stewart, G. L., & Barrick, M. R. (2000). Team structure and performance: Assessing the mediating role of intrateam process and the moderating role of task type. *Academy of Management journal*, 43(2), 135-148.
- Sundstrom, E. (2000). *Supporting work team effectiveness*. JosseyBass.
- Sutarno, S., Setiawan, A., Kaniawati, I., & Suhandi, A. (2017). Pre-service physics teachers' problem-solving skills in projectile motion concept. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*,
- Tarricone, P., & Luca, J. (2002). Employees, teamwork and social interdependence—a formula for successful business? *Team performance management: An International journal*.
- Tu, Y., Lu, X., & Yu, Y. (2017). Supervisors' ethical leadership and employee job satisfaction: A social cognitive perspective. *Journal of Happiness Studies*, 18, 229-245.
- Udida, L., Basse, U., Udofia, I., & Egbona, E. (2009). System performance and sustainability of higher education in Nigeria. 11th International Conference of Educational Management Association of South Africa (EMASA),
- Yukl, G. (2006). *Leadership in Organizations* (6th ed.). Pearson- Prentice.